

IMPERIAL

**The differential initiation of transcripts with
different stability**

National Heart and Lung Institute, Imperial College London

September 2025

**Supervised by Dr. Sviatoslav Sidorov,
MRC Laboratory of Medical Sciences**

**Submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirement of the degree of MSc in
Genomic Medicine**

Word counts: 6729

Statement of Originality

I certify that this thesis, and the research to which it refers, are the product of my own work, conducted during the current year of the MSc in Genomic Medicine at Imperial College London. Any ideas or quotations from the work of other people, published or otherwise, or from my own previous work are fully acknowledged in accordance with the standard referencing practices of the discipline.

In this study, I used a custom bioinformatics pipeline for CAGE data processing and analysis that was developed in the laboratories of Professors Boris Lenhard and Anthony Mathelier before I started this project.

Acknowledgements

I would like to thank my supervisor, Dr. Sviatoslav Sidorov, for his continuous guidance throughout this research project. His enthusiasm for science inspires me every day, and without his patience and encouragement in the face of my mistakes, I would not have been able to complete this work.

I would like to thank the group leader, Professor Boris Lenhard, whose insights and knowledge of the subject matter helped guide me through this research.

I would like to thank the rest of the Computational Regulatory Genomics group for their help, valuable suggestions, and for making my time in the lab so enjoyable.

Finally, I would especially like to thank my parents for their unwavering support and encouragement. Your love empowers me, as always.

Abstract

Alternative transcription start site (TSS) usage can produce transcript isoforms with varying stability. However, it is still unknown how the TSS choice and promoter sequence features may affect transcript stability. To investigate this, I compared steady-state RNA captured by Cap Analysis of Gene Expression (CAGE) with nascent RNA captured by Native Elongating Transcript–CAGE (NET-CAGE) across five human cell lines. Using a custom Nextflow pipeline integrated with CAGEr, I processed raw sequencing data, performed TSS calling, normalization, and clustering, and created a UCSC Genome Browser track hub to visualize promoter architectures. Quality control confirmed high sequencing performance across replicates, though certain systematic biases were still observed. NET-CAGE libraries consistently contained a small number of extremely highly expressed TSSs, mainly from *MALAT1*, *NEAT1*, and *SCARNA2*, which skewed dinucleotide distributions. After excluding these extremely highly expressed signals, re-analysis revealed systematic shifts between CAGE and NET-CAGE datasets, and the observed patterns remained significant after statistical testing, even after removal of highly abundant chromatin-retained RNAs. This work highlights both technical artifacts and biological differences in promoter sequence usage between nascent and steady-state RNA fractions. The results suggest that TSS choice and promoter grammar may influence transcript stability, demonstrate differential representation of specific TSSs and 5'-end dinucleotides between nascent and steady-state RNA fractions, and provide insights to guide future studies.

Table of Contents

Abbreviations.....	5
1. Introduction.....	6
1.1 Transcription initiation.....	6
1.2 High-throughput sequencing methods to study transcription initiation.....	7
1.3 Transcript stability.....	8
1.4 Aims of the study.....	9
2. Material and Methods.....	11
2.1 CAGE and NET-CAGE RNA sequencing data.....	11
2.2 Data preprocessing and quality control.....	12
2.2.1 Mapping Step.....	12
2.2.2 CAGEr Step.....	12
2.3 Track Hub Construction for the UCSC Genome Browser.....	13
2.4 Analysis of Highly Expressed TSSs in NET-CAGE samples.....	14
2.5 Dinucleotide Analysis.....	15
3. Results.....	16
3.1 Quality Control of CAGE and NET-CAGE data.....	16
3.2 TSS Quality Report.....	21
3.3 Track Hub Inspection.....	26
3.4 Frequencies of dinucleotide initiators in CAGE and NET-CAGE samples.....	28
4. Discussion.....	39
References.....	44

Abbreviations

TSS	Transcription start site
RNAPII	RNA polymerase II
CAGE	Cap Analysis of Gene Expression
nAnT-iCAGE	Non-Amplification non-Tagging Illumina CAGE
ssDNA	Single-stranded DNA
dsDNA	Double-stranded DNA
uaRNAs	Upstream Antisense RNAs
eRNAs	Enhancer RNAs
NET-CAGE	Native Elongating Transcript–Cap Analysis of Gene Expression
RNAPII	RNA polymerase II
TPM	Transcripts Per Million
PCA	Principal Component Analysis
ELP4	Elongator acetyltransferase complex subunit 4
H3C12	H3 Clustered Histone 12
lncRNA	long non-coding RNA
MALAT1	Metastasis-Associated Lung Adenocarcinoma Transcript 1
NEAT1	Nuclear enriched abundant transcript 1
SCARNA2	Small Cajal body-associated RNA 2
DSB	Double-Strand Break

1. Introduction

1.1 Transcription initiation

A transcription start site (TSS) is the first base of a gene to be transcribed by an RNA polymerase, corresponding to the 5'-end base of the resulting transcript (1). Numerous studies found that in animals, plants and fungi, RNA polymerase II (RNAPII) initiates transcription predominantly from pyrimidine-purine dinucleotides ($Y_{-1}R_{+1} = \{CA, CG, TA, TG\}$), where R_{+1} (A or G) is the first base of the transcript and Y_{-1} (C or T) is the preceding genomic base (2-7). Such dinucleotides and, in general, any characteristic transcription initiation motifs (which can be wider than the core dinucleotide) are called initiator motifs, or simply initiators (8). Due to their prevalence, $Y_{-1}R_{+1}$ initiators are called canonical. Additionally, RNAPII can initiate transcription from a stretch of pyrimidines called the TCT initiator. In its shortest form, this initiator motif can be summarised as $Y_{-1}C_{+1}T_{+2}$. It is characteristic for the TSSs of genes encoding translation-related proteins (7). Interestingly, recent studies demonstrated that the canonical and TCT initiators frequently coincide in the same promoter (9, 10).

One or more TSSs define the promoter region of a transcribed gene. Promoter sequence guides the initiation of transcription by providing binding sites for the RNA polymerase and general transcription factors. In the human genome, CAGE has revealed two major shapes of RNAPII promoters (2, 8). "Sharp", or "narrow", promoters are characterised by a single well-defined TSS, often accompanied by a TATA box located approximately 30 bp upstream. Typically, TAT -box-dependent sharp promoters drive the transcription of tissue-specific genes (8) or histone genes (11). Importantly, genes of translation-related proteins have a separate category of sharp promoters, without the TATA box but with a TCT initiator. In contrast, "broad", or "dispersed" promoters are defined by the presence of multiple TSSs distributed across a wider genomic region and are typical of many housekeeping genes and genes encoding developmental regulators (8).

1.2 High-throughput sequencing methods to study transcription initiation

To detect TSSs of capped transcripts across the genome, Cap Analysis of Gene Expression (CAGE) is widely used. By capturing RNA molecules with a 5'-cap and sequencing their 5'-ends, CAGE allows both precise mapping of TSSs across the genome and quantification of their expression levels (12). Furthermore, TSS profiling facilitates the identification of promoter regions, enabling comparative analysis of TSS and promoter usage under different cellular conditions.

The current, widely used, CAGE protocol is non-Amplification non-Tagging Illumina CAGE (nAnt-iCAGE) (10). The workflow can be divided into the following steps:

1. Random primed reverse transcription to synthesize DNA from RNA.
2. Biotinization at oxidated diol residues of the cap structure of RNA.
3. RNase I digestion of the single-stranded overhangs of the RNA molecules.
4. Capture of the biotinylated cap using magnetic streptavidin beads.
5. Wash unbound RNA/DNA hybrid molecules.
6. Release of single-stranded DNA (ssDNA) from capped RNA/DNA hybrid molecules.
7. Ligation of a barcoded 5' linker to the ssDNA.
8. Ligation of a 3' linker.
9. Synthesis of the second strand of the DNA using a primer annealed to the 5' linker.
10. The resulting double-stranded DNA molecules (dsDNA) constitute the sequencing library.

Compared to the original CAGE protocol, nAnT-iCAGE eliminates both PCR amplification of cDNA and restriction enzyme tagging, thereby reducing potential procedural biases introduced during library preparation.

However, RNA abundance in a cell is dynamically regulated by both its synthesis and degradation. As a result, conventional CAGE captures only the steady-state levels of RNA and may fail to detect unstable transcripts, such as upstream antisense RNAs (uaRNAs) or enhancer RNAs (eRNAs), which are rapidly degraded after synthesis. Therefore, Native Elongating Transcript–Cap Analysis of Gene Expression (NET-CAGE) was developed to capture a snapshot of RNA that is being synthesized (nascent RNA) and more accurately reflects the transcriptional activity of promoters (13).

The NET-CAGE protocol mainly exploits the property of nascent RNA being tightly bound to RNA polymerase II (RNAPII) on chromatin to quantify newly transcribed RNA. The process begins by isolating the insoluble nuclear fraction that contains RNA-RNAPII-DNA complexes from the nuclei. Then, chromatin digestion is performed to release the nascent RNA. To prevent transcription from continuing during the procedure, α -amanitin is continuously included in the buffer to inhibit transcription run-on. After that, nascent RNA is sequenced at the 5'-end using the CAGE protocol. In the study that introduced NET-CAGE (13), the NET-CAGE data and CAGE data on total RNA were produced using the same CAGE protocol.

1.3 Transcript stability

Transcripts produced by different genes can have different stabilities defined as the times of their half-life. Among mRNAs, those produced by genes associated with cell cycle regulation and transcription are much less stable than those produced by biosynthesis-related genes (14). Later studies confirmed these results, showing lower stability of mRNAs produced by genes encoding transcription factors, signalling proteins and chromatin modifiers, as well as

by genes with functions specific to the cell cycle (15-17). In contrast, the same studies demonstrated higher stability of transcripts produced by genes related to metabolism, respiration, translation, cellular structure and homeostasis, defence response and proteolysis (15-17). The stability of mRNA also depends on its sequence characteristics, positively correlating with the number of splice junctions, normalised by the length of the open reading frame, and negatively correlating with the presence of CpG dinucleotides in the 5'-UTR and the AU-rich elements or PUF-binding motifs in the 3'-UTR (15). Additionally, capping, polyadenylation and efficient translation stabilise RNA molecules (18-20).

Profiling of the half-lives of hundreds of long non-coding RNAs (lncRNAs) in mouse revealed that their stability ranges from extremely low (for example, the half-life of *Neat1* was less than 2 hours) to extremely high (*Zfas1* produced a non-coding RNA with the half-life of more than 16 hours) (21). In addition, similar to mRNAs or regulatory genes, regulatory non-coding RNAs were demonstrated to be short-lived (22). Furthermore, enhancer RNAs were demonstrated to be unstable as well (23).

Based on the characteristics of the nAnT-iCAGE and NET-CAGE protocols, transcripts with short half-lives are expected to be enriched in NET-CAGE, whereas transcripts with longer half-lives are expected to be enriched in CAGE. Therefore, a comparison of the TSSs expression between NET-CAGE and total RNA CAGE datasets can serve as an approach to estimate transcript stability.

1.4 Aims of the study

Many genes in the human genome have multiple TSSs, and the alternative selection of a TSS produces different transcript isoforms (24). However, it is still unknown how the TSS choice may affect transcript stability. The aim of our study is to do an initial exploratory analysis of a relationship between the properties of the TSS and the stability of the

respective transcript, using publicly available sequencing data from the total and nascent fractions of capped RNA from several widely-used human cell lines.

2. Material and Methods

2.1 CAGE and NET-CAGE RNA sequencing data

In this study, we used CAGE and NET-CAGE single-end sequencing data from five *Homo sapiens* cell lines: MCF-7, GM12878, HeLa-S3, HepG2, and K652 (13). The datasets we used are summarized in Table 1. For each cell line, CAGE data were derived from two replicates without urea treatment, while NET-CAGE data were derived from multiple replicates that differed by the urea concentration used to purify the insoluble nuclear fraction. For instance, in HepG2 cell line, three urea molarity steps (0.5 M, 1 M, 2 M) were applied, each with two treated replicates, whereas only two replicates were available for CAGE.

Table 1. Overview of CAGE and NET-CAGE data

Cell Type	Number of Samples	GSM Accession
MCF-7	2 CAGE; 14 NET-CAGE	GSM3318135 GSM3318136 GSM3318137 GSM3318138 GSM3318139 GSM3318140 GSM3318141 GSM3318142 GSM3318143 GSM3318144 GSM3318145 GSM3318146 GSM3318147 GSM3318148 GSM3318149 GSM3318150
GM12878	2 CAGE; 14 NET-CAGE	GSM3318207 GSM3318208 GSM3318209 GSM3318210 GSM3318211 GSM3318212 GSM3318213 GSM3318214 GSM3318215 GSM3318216 GSM3318217 GSM3318218 GSM3318219 GSM3318220 GSM3318221 GSM3318222
HeLa-S3	2 CAGE; 6 NET-CAGE	GSM3318223 GSM3318224 GSM3318225 GSM3318226 GSM3318227 GSM3318228 GSM3318229 GSM3318230
HepG2	2 CAGE; 6 NET-CAGE	GSM3318231 GSM3318232 GSM3318233 GSM3318234 GSM3318235 GSM3318236 GSM3318237 GSM3318238
K562	2 CAGE; 6 NET-CAGE	GSM3318239 GSM3318240 GSM3318241 GSM3318242 GSM3318243 GSM3318244 GSM3318245 GSM3318246

All the expression data utilized in this study can be retrieved from Gene Expression Omnibus, under accession GSE118075.

2.2 Data preprocessing and quality control

We processed raw CAGE and NET-CAGE sequencing data using a custom Nextflow pipeline previously developed in the lab. The pipeline consists of two major steps: read mapping and downstream processing with CAGEr.

2.2.1 Mapping Step

The mapping step generates intermediate results and allows for initial quality assessment of the raw data. It includes the following processes:

1. Raw sequence data quality control with FastQC (version 0.11.9), providing an overview of potential quality issues prior to downstream analysis.
2. Adapter trimming with TrimGalore (version 0.6.7).
3. Trimming of one G base from the 5' ends of reads (forward reads, in the case of paired-end reads) with cutadapt (version 4.6), characteristic of CAGE reads obtained from capped transcripts.
4. Read mapping to the reference genome with STAR (version 2.7.10a).
5. Mapping quality assessment with Samtools (version 1.19.2), as well as sorting and indexing of the obtained BAM files.
6. Generation of separate bigWig files for the forward and reverse strand for each sample to serve as input for the CAGEr processing step.
7. Aggregation of raw read and mapping quality control reports with MultiQC (version 1.14) to generate a single summary report across all samples.

2.2.2 CAGEr Step

The CAGEr step produces the final outputs, including the CAGEexp (CAGEr) object with the coordinates and normalised expression levels of all TSSs, as well as corresponding genome-wide tracks. This step involves the following processes:

1. Creation of an initial CAGEr object containing TSSs with the corresponding raw read counts, using the input bigWig files generated in the previous step.
2. Per-sample annotation of TSSs by the type of genomic region (promoter, exon, intron or intergenic), using the plotAnnot() function from the CAGEr R package (version 2.14.0).
3. Power-law TPM normalization of raw TSS expression levels, using the normalizeTagCount() function in CAGEr.
4. Identification of TSS clusters with the distclu() function in CAGEr.
5. Annotation of TSS clusters by the type of genomic region with the ChiPseeker R package.
6. Aggregation of TSS clusters located close to each other and passing a TPM threshold into consensus clusters across different samples, using the aggregateTagClusters() function in CAGEr.
7. Generation of a CAGEr object, together with track files in the bigWig and BED formats, for downstream analysis.

2.3 Track Hub Construction for the UCSC Genome Browser

The University of California, Santa Cruz (UCSC) Genome Browser is one of the most widely used interactive online tools for visualization and analysis of genomic data. It provides access to various annotation data and allows users to add custom tracks and create custom, self-hosted sets of tracks called track hubs (25).

To build a track hub showing per-sample TSS coordinates and normalized expression levels, as well as consensus TSS clusters, I used the easyTrackHubs R package (version 0.0.0.9012). Since the UCSC Genome Browser does not support BED files in track hubs, I first converted the consensus cluster track from the BED format into the binary indexed bigBed format, using the bedToBigBed command, after removing the header and sorting the entries. I then specified the label and color of each track, along with the file format and

reference genome, using the `easyTrackHubs` function. In total, 112 bigWig files containing normalized expression levels of TSSs from both strands of 56 samples, and one bigBed file containing consensus clusters, were combined with the track hub configuration files in a single directory named “rna_tss_trackhub”, which was uploaded to an Internet-accessible server.

Once configured, the track hub can be viewed in the UCSC Genome Browser by importing the URL of the hub.txt file (26)

2.4 Analysis of Highly Expressed TSSs in NET-CAGE samples

During the investigation of TSSs highly-expressed in NET-CAGE samples, I performed data analysis in R. I used the `BSgenome.Hsapiens.UCSC.hg38` R package (version 1.4.4), containing the sequence of the hg38 human genome assembly, and the [org.Hs.eg.db](#) R package (version 3.14.0), providing human genome annotation resources.

For operations with genomic coordinates, I used the `GenomicRanges` R package (version 1.46.1). To import bigWig files into the R environment, I used the `import()` function from the `rtracklayer` R package (version 1.54.0). Also, I used the `ChIPseeker` R package (version 1.34.1) to annotate the TSSs with the respective genes by defining promoter regions as -150 to +150 bp around the annotated starting positions of all the same-strand 5'-UTRs of all genes and assigning each TSS to the genes in whose core promoter regions it fell.

For CAGE-specific operations, I used the `CAGEr` R package (version 2.2) which is specifically designed for CAGE data processing and promoterome mining (27).

For the general data manipulation, I mainly used the `dplyr` R package (versions 1.0.7 and 1.0.10). For string-related operations, I used the `stringr` R package (version 1.4.0), and for reordering factor levels – the `forcats` R package (version 0.5.2) provides tools for.

For data visualization, I used the ggplot2 R package (version 3.5.2), as well as the cowplot R package (version 1.2.0), the latter one – to extend the ggplot2 functionality with themes and to arrange multiple figures into one grid layout. Additionally, I used the ggrepel R package (version 0.9.1) to prevent overlapping of text labels. Furthermore, I used magick (version 2.8.7) to read PDF files as image objects.

2.5 Dinucleotide Analysis

To test whether the differences in the 5-prime dinucleotide frequencies between CAGE and NET-CAGE samples were statistically significant, I applied the Mann-Whitney U test (also known as the Wilcoxon rank-sum test) using the R function `wilcox.test()`. This nonparametric test assesses whether two independent groups differ significantly without assuming a normal distribution (28). After obtaining raw p -values for all 16 dinucleotides, I adjusted them using the Benjamini-Hochberg procedure (29) with the R function `p.adjust()`, to control the false discovery rate. Finally, by applying an adjusted p -value threshold of 0.01, I determined which observed differences in dinucleotide frequencies between CAGE and NET-CAGE were significant.

3. Results

3.1 Quality Control of CAGE and NET-CAGE data

To study the interplay between transcription start sites (TSSs) and transcript stability in the human genome, we used publicly available CAGE and NET-CAGE datasets from cell lines MCF-7, GM12878, HeLa-S3, HepG2, and K652 (Table 1 in Materials and Methods) (13). To assess the quality of the samples and preprocess them for further analysis, I ran a custom Nextflow pipeline previously developed at the lab and analysed the output quality reports.

In all the five cell lines, the mean quality scores across the read length are consistently high (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Phred scores of the MCF-7 CAGE and NET-CAGE libraries.

Also, in all the five cell lines, the STAR alignment results show that most reads are uniquely mapped, with only a tiny proportion unmapped, indicating a high library quality (Figure 2).

STAR: Alignment Scores

Created with MultiQC

Figure 2. Numbers of mapped and unmapped reads in each HeLa-S3 sample.

In general, the read quality across all the cell lines is high. However, we observed certain systematic patterns between cell lines which point to possible limitations in our analysis or pose interesting questions.

For instance, the MultiQC reports provide the proportions of the four standard DNA bases across the read length for each sample (Figure 3). The first position shows the highest proportion of guanine, which means that adapters have already been trimmed from the 5'-end of the reads and that the cap-dependent guanine became the first base (30, 31). This is considered a hallmark of successful library preparation in CAGE and NET-CAGE protocols. However, it is worth noting that the second position also shows a predominance of guanine, which may indicate an also known property of the reverse transcriptase to sometimes add more than one non-templated, cap-dependent nucleotides (30). Therefore, our trimming of one 5'-G may still retain cap-dependent guanines at the 5'-ends of some reads, which may shift positions of a subset of called TSSs across the genome. However,

such TSSs would have a "G" at the -1 position, clearly indicating that such TSS is not marked by a canonical (pyrimidine-purine) or a pyrimidine-rich initiator and, hence, likely not a real TSS.

Figure 3. An example per-base nucleotide content in a HepG2 NET-CAGE replicate.

Per-base nucleotide frequencies in the other five NET-CAGE and CAGE libraries are very similar.

Notably, in the MCF-7 and GM12878 cell lines, both derived from females, a proportion of reads mapped to the Y chromosome. Given the presumably female karyotype of these cells, such reads may originate from the pseudoautosomal region of the X chromosome.

Interestingly, the proportions of these reads are lower in CAGE samples than in NET-CAGE samples for both cell lines (Figure 4, 5). This may indicate that pseudoautosomal transcripts have low stability, or that in the CAGE samples, the high overall RNA expression of certain genes (actively producing stable transcripts) reduces the relative proportion of sequencing reads originating from other genes, including those from the pseudoautosomal region.

Figure 4. The proportions of X-chromosome and Y-chromosome mapped reads in GM12878.

Figure 5. The proportions of X-chromosome and Y-chromosome mapped reads in MCF-7.

Furthermore, the dominant peak of the GC-content distribution of CAGE reads is systematically shifted towards lower values, in comparison to the dominant peak of NET-CAGE reads (Figure 6, 7). Moreover, we observed a lower sharp peak at a GC-content position of about 32 only in the NET-CAGE samples. According to the FastQC manual, such sharp extra peaks are usually the result of contamination with a specific GC-content, such as adapter dimers (32). However, our FastQC reports did not show a noticeable adapter contamination, which suggests that the observed NET-CAGE specific low-GC-peaks are produced by some AT-rich unstable transcripts.

Figure 6. GC-content distributions of CAGE (green) and NET-CAGE (orange and red) reads from HepG2 samples.

Figure 7. GC-content distributions of CAGE (green) and NET-CAGE (red) reads from MCF-7 samples.

Overall, the CAGE and NET-CAGE sequencing reads used in this study are of good quality and, therefore, suitable for the downstream analysis. However, the observations made above warrant further investigation. They may reflect technical properties of the CAGE and NET-CAGE protocols that should be taken into account or biological phenomena that are not yet fully understood.

3.2 TSS Quality Report

After mapping the CAGE and NET-CAGE data to the reference genome, I ran the second part of the same custom pipeline on each individual cell line to call TSSs and check their quality. During this process, some additional analyses were produced and summarized in quality control reports.

First, in each sample, I called TSSs and annotated them with the type of genomic region where they reside (Figure 8). Overall, all samples from the five cell lines show a reasonable

distribution of tags across genomic elements. Namely, as expected for protocols that target transcription initiation regions, the majority of TSSs called from the CAGE and NET-CAGE data mapped to promoters. Some TSSs were also found in exonic, intronic and intergenic regions. These may originate from enhancers, as enhancers are dispersed across the non-coding regions of the human genome and can also occur within introns (33) Additionally, the proportions of TSSs mapping to non-promoter regions are smaller in CAGE samples, than in NET-CAGE samples, likely because eRNAs are normally fast-degrading .

Figure 8. TSS annotation of each GM12878 sample.

Then, I normalized the raw read counts per TSS according to the power-law distribution (34). The total number of tags after normalization was scaled to 10^6 to express the normalized transcription levels in Transcripts Per Million (TPM). When I plotted the number of TSSs (along the y axis) with at least a given number of reads ("tags", along the x axis), I observed long "tails" at the lower right ends of these curves for NET-CAGE samples in all cell lines (Figure 9). These "tails" indicate the existence of a very small number of TSSs with

exceptionally high expression levels in the NET-CAGE samples, but not in CAGE samples, a pattern that warranted further investigation in my subsequent analyses.

Figure 9. The number of TSSs (or "CTSSs", meaning "CAGE TSSs") supported by at least a given number of CAGE reads (tags) in the K562 CAGE and NET-CAGE samples.

After the normalization, I clustered neighbouring TSSs to obtain a set of core promoter regions. The interquantile widths of these clusters revealed two distinct groups of core promoters by their size (Figure 10). One group comprises "sharp", or "narrow", promoters, characterized by a single well-defined TSS (the left sharp peak in Figure 10), and the other group comprises "broad" promoters, characterized by multiple TSSs distributed across a wider promoter region (the right broad peak in Figure 10). The existence of the two groups of core promoters is well known (8)

Figure 10. The interquantile width distribution of TSS clusters ("tag clusters") in the HepG2 CAGE and NET-CAGE samples.

Next, I generated consensus clusters by aggregating tag clusters from different samples that are in close vicinity. Figure 11 shows the number of consensus clusters per sample in the CAGE and NET-CAGE samples from HeLa-S3. Taking into account the fact that the human genome has ~20,000 coding genes, as well as tens of thousands of non-coding genes and enhancers (35-37), the obtained numbers of consensus clusters are reasonable, as we do not expect all the genes to be transcribed at the same time and in the same cell type, while enhancers also tend to be tissue / cell type-specific (38, 39), with ubiquitously active enhancers likely comprising only a minor proportion (40).

Figure 11. The number of non-zero consensus clusters per sample, as well as the total number of consensus clusters across all samples ("Union") in HeLa-S3.

Finally, I performed principal component analysis (PCA) on all samples, using the top 500 most variable consensus clusters. Figure 12 shows the clustering of samples from MCF-7. Apart from two CAGE samples separated from NET-CAGE samples (as expected), the NET-CAGE samples treated with urea in different concentrations, or different replicates treated with the same concentration (2M in this case), formed two separate groups. In general, one group consists of samples treated with lower urea concentrations, while the other comprises samples treated by higher concentrations. This pattern suggests a biological effect of different urea concentrations of the genome-wide TSS expression pattern.

Figure 12. PCA of MCF-7 samples, based on the genome-wide power-law-normalized TSS expression levels (in TPM). across. The variance explained by each principal component is shown in the brackets.

3.3 Track Hub Inspection

To further ensure data quality, I created a track hub in the UCSC Genome Browser to inspect TSS initiator motifs and TSS distributions in the promoters of different types:

http://trackhub2.genereg.net/rna_tss_trackhub/hub.txt

Our inspection of housekeeping and developmental genes, as well as TATA box-dependent and independent genes with narrow promoters, revealed expected promoter shapes and initiator motifs. For example, *ELP4* (Elongator acetyltransferase complex subunit 4), a housekeeping gene encoding a non-ribosomal protein, shows a clear broad promoter architecture across samples in our track hub (Figure 13). In contrast, *H3C12* (H3 Clustered

Histone 12), a histone-encoding gene, displays a sharp promoter with a TATA box located 32 bp upstream on the minus strand (Figure 14).

Figure 13. Broad promoter architecture of *ELP4* across multiple CAGE and NET-CAGE samples from five different cell lines.

Figure 14. Sharp promoter architecture of *H3C12* in CAGE samples from MCF-7 and GM12878, and NET-CAGE samples from MCF-7, GM12878, and K562.

To facilitate the future studies of transcription initiation and RNA fragment recapping genome-wide in five widely used human cell lines, we provide our track hub as a public resource for the scientific community, accessible at http://trackhub2.genereg.net/rna_tss_trackhub/hub.txt.

3.4 Frequencies of dinucleotide initiators in CAGE and NET-CAGE samples

The analysis of expression-weighted dinucleotide frequencies at the 5'-ends for CAGE and NET-CAGE reads is an important step in the quality control of this type of sequencing data, as the dominance of the dinucleotides corresponding to the canonical (pyrimidine-purine, or YR) transcription initiators, followed by the high frequencies of pyrimidine-pyrimidine (YY) dinucleotides, corresponding to non-canonical initiators characteristic of ribosomal proteins, suggests that the CAGE (or NET-CAGE) library captured the true transcription initiation profile in the sample. Apart from quality control, we motivated our dinucleotide analysis by a private communication from Pavel Nikitin, a student also supervised by Dr. Sviatoslav Sidorov, in which Pavel reported systematic differences in the frequencies of the 5'-dinucleotides between some CAGE and NET-CAGE samples. Specifically, he observed that the expression-weighted frequencies of the CA, CC, TC, CT and TT dinucleotides were higher in CAGE samples, whereas the frequencies of the CG, TG and TA dinucleotides were higher in NET-CAGE samples. In addition, he noticed a higher frequency of presumably non-initiator dinucleotides AG, AA and AC in CAGE samples. While the higher frequency of the YY initiators in CAGE data is expected due to the known high stability of transcripts encoding ribosomal proteins, the rest of the reported differences could not be readily explained. Pavel and Sviatoslav hypothesized that these differences stemmed from different stabilities of transcripts produced from different initiators. However, for his analysis, Pavel used CAGE data from primary cell lines and NET-CAGE data from cancer/immortalized cell lines, which precluded the direct comparison of the dinucleotide frequencies in the two datasets. We realised that, doing the present study, we are in a perfect position to verify Pavel's observations, as we use CAGE and NET-CAGE samples from the same cell lines.

In order to do this, I ran the CAGEr step of the custom pipeline on all the obtained bigWig files from all the considered cell lines to generate a single CAGEr object containing all samples. Using this object, I plotted the bar chart of the expression-weighted dinucleotide

frequencies calculated across all samples after normalizing the TSS expression levels (Figure 15).

Figure 15. The initial per-sample expression-weighted dinucleotide frequencies across all CAGE (blue) and NET-CAGE (orange) samples from all the cell lines.

In agreement with Pavel's results, we observed that the TA dinucleotide had lower expression-weighted frequencies in CAGE samples, than in NET-CAGE samples. However, this pattern was not as clear for the CG and TG dinucleotides (Figure 15). Also, as expected and in line with Pavel's observations, we detected the higher frequencies of the CC, TC, CT and TT initiators in CAGE samples (Figure 15). In addition, we observed a higher frequency

of AG and AC in CAGE samples but no clear bias for the AA dinucleotide. However, in a sharp contrast to Pavel's observations, CA was much more frequent in NET-CAGE than in CAGE, suggesting that Pavel's opposite results was an artifact of using CAGE and NET-CAGE data from different cell types. In total, our results mostly support Pavel's observations, calling for an investigation of the unexpected frequency biases of the canonical initiators and other dinucleotides.

From the long “tails” of the NET-CAGE TSS count distributions, calculated across normalized TSS expression levels (Figure 9), we inferred that there must exist a small number of TSSs that are extremely highly expressed specifically in NET-CAGE samples and, therefore, might contribute disproportionately to the expression of certain dinucleotides, thereby skewing their frequencies. To clearly illustrate the presence of such TSSs, we generated the cumulative expression curves for the top 2,000 highest-expressed TSSs in each CAGE and NET-CAGE sample (Figure 16). We observed that in NET-CAGE samples the highest-expressed TSS accounts for a larger proportion of the total expression, compared to CAGE samples. We also observed that for the top TSS ranks, the cumulative expression curve in CAGE samples is much more gradual than in NET-CAGE samples, which clearly illustrates the existence of TSSs that are extremely highly expressed in NET-CAGE samples but not in CAGE samples.

Figure 16. Cumulative expression proportion distributions for the top 2,000 TSSs ranked by their total expression proportions in two CAGE samples (A, B) and two NET-CAGE samples (C, D) from the HeLa-S3 and K562 cell lines.

Considering the presence of extremely highly expressed TSSs, it is meaningful to determine which genes they originate from and which dinucleotides they contain. For each NET-CAGE sample, we selected the top 50 most highly expressed TSSs and manually annotated each TSS by defining its promoter region as ± 50 bp around its position and identifying reference genes whose annotated transcription start sites fall within this region. These genes were then considered as the genes corresponding to the respective TSSs. We then manually corrected TSS-gene assignments in special cases, such as when more than one gene was assigned to a single TSS. Finally, we calculated the mean rank and the full range of ranks for

each TSS among the top 50 TSSs in each cell line. Figure 17 shows the rank distributions of the top 10 TSSs in HeLa-S3.

Figure 17. Rank distributions of the top 10 highest expressed TSSs in HeLa-S3. The red dot indicates the mean rank, and the whiskers represent the full range of the TSS ranks. The y-axis shows the genomic positions of the TSSs, along with their strand, corresponding dinucleotides and assigned genes.

Figure 17 demonstrates that the highest (smallest) ranks are assigned to TSSs of three long non-coding RNA (lncRNA) genes, *MALAT1* (Metastasis-Associated Lung Adenocarcinoma Transcript 1), *NEAT1* (Nuclear enriched abundant transcript 1) and *SCARNA2* (Small Cajal body-associated RNA 2). To check if this is the general trend, we selected TSSs with the mean per-cell-line rank less or equal to 10, and counted the number of cell lines in which they had such a high rank (Figure 18). We found that the same three lncRNA genes are consistently ranked among the top 10 in more than three cell lines.

Figure 18. TSSs with a mean rank less than or equal to 10 in at least one of the five cell lines. For each TSS, the x-axis shows the number of cell lines in which it achieved a mean rank less than or equal to 10.

Therefore, we decided to exclude the extremely highly expressed TSSs to observe dinucleotide frequency distributions without their influence. To determine how many TSSs should be removed, we calculated the proportion of the total expression corresponding to the top 50 highest expressed TSSs across all NET-CAGE samples (Figure 19). Although the samples showed slightly proportion distributions, considering all samples together, the slope of the curve began to level off at a proportion of approximately 0.001. Based on that, we set the total expression cutoff at 0.001 to remove all TSSs with the expression proportion higher than that.

Figure 19. Expression proportions of the top 50 highest-expressed TSSs in NET-CAGE samples from MCF-7 (A) and HepG2 (B).

Next, we selected all TSSs that contributed more than 0.001 of the total expression found across all NET-CAGE samples, and took their union, which gave a total of 54 TSSs. We then exclude this union set from all samples, including both CAGE ones. After this filtering, the updated cumulative plots of the top-expressed TSSs in NET-CAGE samples exhibit a pattern similar to that seen in CAGE samples (compare Figure 20A-B to Figure 16A-B).

Figure 20. Cumulative expression proportion distributions for the top 2,000 TSSs ranked by their total expression proportions in two NET-CAGE samples (A, B) from the HeLa-S3 and K562 cell lines, after the removal of the 54 extremely highly expressed TSSs.

Figure 21. The expression-weighted dinucleotide frequencies across all samples within per cell line, after the removal of 54 extremely highly expressed TSSs.

Following this exclusion, we performed the power-law normalization on the raw expression values of the remaining TSSs and re-calculated the dinucleotide frequency distributions (Figure 21). To statistically evaluate the differences in dinucleotide frequencies between CAGE and NET-CAGE samples both before and after the TSS filtering, we assessed the

shift between the CAGE and NET-CAGE distributions for each dinucleotide using the Mann-Whitney U test. Table 2 presents the p -values for each dinucleotide after adjustment with the Benjamini-Hochberg procedure. Using a threshold of 0.01, we identified dinucleotides with a significant difference between their proportions in CAGE and NET-CAGE samples. The significant adjusted p -values are given in bold in Table 2.

Table 2. Benjamini-Hochberg-adjusted p -values from the Mann-Whitney U test for each dinucleotide before and after the exclusion of the 54 extremely highly expressed TSSs.

Dinucleotide	Adjusted p -value <i>before</i> exclusion	Adjusted p -value <i>after</i> exclusion
CA	6.34×10^{-5}	8.99×10^{-10}
CG	0.87	0.47
TG	0.16	9.71×10^{-2}
GG	0.11	0.31
TA	5.99×10^{-10}	5.54×10^{-2}
GA	0.86	0.36
CC	4.49×10^{-10}	8.97×10^{-10}
GC	5.29×10^{-4}	9.71×10^{-4}
GT	1.74×10^{-4}	6.79×10^{-2}
AG	7.92×10^{-4}	1.55×10^{-2}
TC	4.49×10^{-10}	8.97×10^{-10}
CT	4.36×10^{-8}	2.55×10^{-7}
AA	0.16	0.39
TT	3.69×10^{-6}	2.74×10^{-5}
AT	0.42	0.36
AC	9.00×10^{-6}	1.50×10^{-5}

Among the canonical, $Y_{-1}R_{+1}$ (pyrimidine-purine), initiators CA and TA showed significantly lower frequencies in CAGE samples independently of the filtering. Based on this result, we hypothesize that $Y_{-1}A_{+1}$ (CA and TA) TSSs tend to produce less stable transcripts than $Y_{-1}G_{+1}$

(CG and TG) TSSs. Indeed, CG demonstrated no significant CAGE vs NET-CAGE usage differences, independently of the filtering, while the difference for TG became significant only after filtering. The latter change is likely due to the rise of the frequency of the TG usage in NET-CAGE samples after excluding the extremely highly expressed dominant TA TSS of *MALAT1*. This explanation is supported by the parallel rise of the CA usage in NET-CAGE samples. Therefore, for both TG and CG, we speculate that they produce transcripts across the stability spectrum.

Next, all the $Y_{-1}Y_{+1}$ (pyrimidine-pyrimidine) initiators displayed the expected significant difference in frequencies between CAGE and NET-CAGE samples. Among other dinucleotides which are unlikely to be real initiators (6), GG, GA, AA, and AT showed no significant difference in frequencies between CAGE and NET-CAGE samples, suggesting that the biological or technical (artificial) processes that give rise to the mapping of reads into these dinucleotides are equally represented in CAGE and NET-CAGE sequencing libraries. Furthermore, GC had higher frequencies in CAGE samples both before and after exclusion; GT initially showed higher frequency in NET-CAGE, but the bias became non-significant after exclusion; AG showed higher frequency in CAGE before exclusion, but the difference also became non-significant after exclusion; AC consistently showed higher frequencies in CAGE than in NET-CAGE across both conditions, which suggests further investigation. Additionally, as a recent study has shown that re-capping occurs in guanine-rich regions (41), we speculate that in dinucleotides such as GG, GA and GT, re-capping is frequent both in nascent and total RNA. In contrast, for GC, re-capping may occur primarily outside the chromatin context. Alternatively, GA, GT and GC may occur if uncapped, G-starting transcripts pollute the sequencing library and produce the G-starting reads, which, after the 5'-G trimming would map into G-starting genomic dinucleotides.

Additionally, the overall ranking of dinucleotides by total proportion remained basically unchanged before and after exclusion, except for GA surpassing TA, which may be

attributed to the removal of the extremely high expression of *MALAT1*, which is transcribed from the TA initiator.

4. Discussion

The relationship between differences in TSS characteristics observed in CAGE and NET-CAGE data and transcript stability remains largely unexplored. Our results contribute to this area of study in several ways. First, we established a publicly accessible UCSC track hub based on five commonly used human cell lines, providing a valuable resource for the research community. Second, we identified the presence of extremely highly expressed TSSs only existing in NET-CAGE samples, which can distort the dinucleotide frequency distribution. Third, we showed that even after removing these highly expressed signals, systematic differences in dinucleotide frequencies between CAGE and NET-CAGE remain, suggesting underlying biological or technical distinctions.

As shown in the Results, the majority of extremely highly expressed signals originate from *MALAT1*, *NEAT1* and *SCARNA2*, which appeared among the top 10 NET-CAGE TSSs in more than three cell lines. These genes encode long noncoding RNAs that are retained in the nucleus and are known to be abundantly expressed in human cells (42, 43). Notably, previous studies have shown that *MALAT1* and *NEAT1* can bind back to chromatin at actively transcribed regions, with distinct localization patterns across the genomes (44). Similarly, *SCARNA2* has been shown to inhibit DNA-dependent protein kinase activity and regulate DNA double-strand break (DSB) repair toward homologous recombination. Subcellular fractionation studies revealed that over 90% of *SCARNA2* is associated with chromatin and accumulates at DSB sites (43), which makes it likely to be captured by NET-CAGE sequencing. Their high transcription activity and localization to the chromatin may explain the extreme abundance in NET-CAGE samples. As transcripts from these genes can occupy a considerable proportion of a nascent RNA library, it decreases the capacity of the library to capture all other genes.

Interestingly, we observed from the track hub that these RNAs are differentially expressed within the cell line. Figure 22 illustrates the difference in expression level of *MALAT1*

between CAGE and NET-CAGE datasets. While *MALAT1* contributes to the highest-expressed signal in the NET-CAGE libraries, it is barely visible in the MCF-7 CAGE libraries. A study on the long non-coding RNA *Malat1* found that it has a long half-life (45), suggesting that its enrichment in NET-CAGE samples is primarily due to its chromatin-associated localization rather than transcript instability.

Figure 22. Differential expression of *MALAT1* TSSs between CAGE and NET-CAGE samples in the MCF-7 cell line.

Around the transcription start site of *NEAT1*, we observed the noticeable variation among different NET-CAGE samples (Figure 23). In the track hub, biological replicates labeled BR1 to BR6 correspond to samples treated with lower urea concentrations, including two replicates treated with 2M urea. In contrast, replicates BR7 to BR14 correspond to those treated with higher urea concentrations, including another two 2M-treated replicates. The visible differences in expression in the track hub correspond exactly to the same sample clustering observed in the PCA plot during quality control (Figure 12), providing further support for the presence of a batch effect. Of note, we also observed a considerable

difference between *NEAT1* expression levels in NET-CAGE vs CAGE sample. Specifically, while in CAGE samples the expression of its dominant TSS ranged from tens to hundreds of TPMs, in NET-CAGE samples the expression of the same TSS ranged from thousands to tens of thousands of TPMs. This observation is in line with the earlier finding that the *Neat1* long non-coding RNA in mouse is extremely unstable (21).

Figure 23. Expression variability of *NEAT1* among MCF-7 NET-CAGE replicates.

For the comparison of dinucleotide frequencies, our initial hypothesis was that the significant shifts observed between the distributions of CAGE- and NET-CAGE-specific dinucleotide frequencies were driven by the presence of extremely highly expressed TSSs in NET-CAGE. Excluding these TSSs indeed eliminated some of the significant shifts, and for dinucleotides where shifts remained, the magnitude of the differences was reduced. This indicates that the initially observed biases were partially attributable to these highly expressed TSSs. However, since significant shifts still persisted, additional factors must be involved. Therefore we propose two hypotheses. The first is that A-starting transcripts are less stable than G-starting

transcripts. However, because the first base of a dinucleotide is not retained in the mature transcript, it remains unclear how the whole dinucleotide could determine transcript stability. An alternative hypothesis is that ribosomal protein genes, which are both highly transcribed and produce stable transcripts, take over a major part of CAGE libraries, thus lowering the expression-weighted proportions of non-YY dinucleotides and thereby producing the observed shifts. To distinguish between these two hypotheses, one could remove all YY-initiating TSSs and re-analyse the dinucleotide frequencies. If the observed shifts become non-significant then, the first hypothesis would be false.

There are several limitations in this study. Regarding the initial selection of data, it is worth noting that certain factors may introduce bias into the downstream analyses. First, urea concentration gradients were not consistent across different cell lines, making some samples not necessarily comparable. Second, the number of biological replicates varied across experimental conditions, which may have contributed to batch effects, as evidenced by both the track hub visualizations and PCA clustering results. Third, the sequencing depth differed among samples, potentially affecting the sensitivity of signal detection. In addition, FastQC reports revealed a predominance of guanine at the second position of the 5' end, which may result from reverse transcriptase adding more than one non-templated and cap-dependent nucleotide. This could introduce bias in downstream analyses. Furthermore, the abnormal GC-content peaks observed remain unexplained, which may reflect unaccounted biological phenomena or technical artifacts introduced during library preparation, and therefore require further investigation. The main limitation of this study lies in the usage of TPM as the measure of expression. Since TPM represents a relative proportion of total signal within each sample, the expression levels of individual TSSs are interdependent. Consequently, an increase or decrease in the expression of a given TSS could be partially influenced by changes in the expression of other TSSs within the same sample, potentially affecting the interpretation of observed differences.

In the future, some related directions warrant further investigation. First, it would be valuable to determine whether transcription initiation at distinct TSSs can drive differences in transcript stability, which can be determined by checking if there exists any shift in dominant TSSs between CAGE and NET-CAGE. Second, the biological relevance of significant biases observed in certain promoter dinucleotide frequencies that do not correspond to known initiator motifs remains to be explored. Third, the differential subcellular localization of transcripts originating from alternative TSSs of the same gene is another factor that may contribute to RNA fate and thus warrants investigation.

In conclusion, this work presents a starting point of an exploratory analysis of the TSS expression signals captured by sequencing of capped transcripts from both nascent and total RNA fractions. We demonstrated the differential representation of certain TSSs and 5'-end dinucleotides between the two RNA fractions, suggested both biological and technical explanations of these phenomena and outlined steps for the future study.

References

1. Policastro RA, Zentner GE. Global approaches for profiling transcription initiation. *Cell Reports Methods*. 2021;1(5).
2. Carninci P, Sandelin A, Lenhard B, Katayama S, Shimokawa K, Ponjavic J, et al. Genome-wide analysis of mammalian promoter architecture and evolution. *Nature genetics*. 2006;38(6):626-35.
3. Chou S-P, Alexander AK, Rice EJ, Choate LA, Danko CG. Genetic dissection of the RNA polymerase II transcription cycle. *Elife*. 2022;11:e78458.
4. Lu Z, Lin Z. The origin and evolution of a distinct mechanism of transcription initiation in yeasts. *Genome research*. 2021;31(1):51-63.
5. Yamamoto YY, Ichida H, Matsui M, Obokata J, Sakurai T, Satou M, et al. Identification of plant promoter constituents by analysis of local distribution of short sequences. *BMC genomics*. 2007;8(1):67.
6. Zhu Y, Vvedenskaya IO, Sze S-H, Nickels BE, Kaplan CD. Quantitative analysis of transcription start site selection reveals control by DNA sequence, RNA polymerase II activity and NTP levels. *Nature Structural & Molecular Biology*. 2024;31(1):190-202.
7. Parry TJ, Theisen JW, Hsu J-Y, Wang Y-L, Corcoran DL, Eustice M, et al. The TCT motif, a key component of an RNA polymerase II transcription system for the translational machinery. *Genes & development*. 2010;24(18):2013-8.
8. Haberle V, Lenhard B, editors. *Promoter architectures and developmental gene regulation*. Seminars in cell & developmental biology; 2016: Elsevier.
9. Wragg JW, White P-L, Hadzhiev Y, Wanigasooriya K, Stodolna A, Tee L, et al. Intra-promoter switch of transcription initiation sites in proliferation signaling-dependent RNA metabolism. *Nature Structural & Molecular Biology*. 2023;30(12):1970-84.
10. Murata M, Nishiyori-Sueki H, Kojima-Ishiyama M, Carninci P, Hayashizaki Y, Itoh M. Detecting expressed genes using CAGE. *Transcription factor regulatory networks: methods and protocols*: Springer; 2014. p. 67-85.
11. Koessler H, Kahle J, Bode C, Doenecke D, Albig W. Human replication-dependent histone H3 genes are activated by a tandemly arranged pair of two CCAAT boxes. *Biochemical Journal*. 2004;384(2):317-26.
12. Takahashi H, Kato S, Murata M, Carninci P. CAGE (cap analysis of gene expression): a protocol for the detection of promoter and transcriptional networks. *Gene Regulatory Networks: Methods and Protocols*: Springer; 2011. p. 181-200.
13. Hirabayashi S, Bhagat S, Matsuki Y, Takegami Y, Uehata T, Kanemaru A, et al. NET-CAGE characterizes the dynamics and topology of human transcribed cis-regulatory elements. *Nature genetics*. 2019;51(9):1369-79.
14. Yang E, van Nimwegen E, Zavolan M, Rajewsky N, Schroeder M, Magnasco M, et al. Decay rates of human mRNAs: correlation with functional characteristics and sequence attributes. *Genome research*. 2003;13(8):1863-72.
15. Sharova LV, Sharov AA, Nedorezov T, Piao Y, Shaik N, Ko MS. Database for mRNA half-life of 19 977 genes obtained by DNA microarray analysis of pluripotent and differentiating mouse embryonic stem cells. *DNA research*. 2009;16(1):45-58.
16. Schwanhäusser B, Busse D, Li N, Dittmar G, Schuchhardt J, Wolf J, et al. Global quantification of mammalian gene expression control. *Nature*. 2011;473(7347):337-42.

17. Herzog VA, Reichholf B, Neumann T, Rescheneder P, Bhat P, Burkard TR, et al. Thiol-linked alkylation of RNA to assess expression dynamics. *Nature methods*. 2017;14(12):1198-204.
18. Drummond DR, Armstrong J, Colman A. The effect of capping and polyadenylation on the stability, movement and translation of synthetic messenger RNAs in *Xenopus* oocytes. *Nucleic acids research*. 1985;13(20):7375-94.
19. Narula A, Ellis J, Taliaferro JM, Rissland OS. Coding regions affect mRNA stability in human cells. *Rna*. 2019;25(12):1751-64.
20. Mukherjee C, Patil DP, Kennedy BA, Bakthavachalu B, Bundschuh R, Schoenberg DR. Identification of cytoplasmic capping targets reveals a role for cap homeostasis in translation and mRNA stability. *Cell reports*. 2012;2(3):674-84.
21. Clark MB, Johnston RL, Inostroza-Ponta M, Fox AH, Fortini E, Moscato P, et al. Genome-wide analysis of long noncoding RNA stability. *Genome research*. 2012;22(5):885-98.
22. Tani H, Mizutani R, Salam KA, Tano K, Ijiri K, Wakamatsu A, et al. Genome-wide determination of RNA stability reveals hundreds of short-lived noncoding transcripts in mammals. *Genome research*. 2012;22(5):947-56.
23. Schwalb B, Michel M, Zacher B, Frühauf K, Demel C, Tresch A, et al. TT-seq maps the human transient transcriptome. *Science*. 2016;352(6290):1225-8.
24. Elgood Hunt E, Vivori C, van Werven FJ. DNA supercoiling impacts alternative transcription start site selection in yeast. *bioRxiv*. 2025:2025.03. 25.645220.
25. Perez G, Barber GP, Benet-Pages A, Casper J, Clawson H, Diekhans M, et al. The UCSC genome browser database: 2025 update. *Nucleic acids research*. 2025;53(D1):D1243-D9.
26. Raney BJ, Dreszer TR, Barber GP, Clawson H, Fujita PA, Wang T, et al. Track data hubs enable visualization of user-defined genome-wide annotations on the UCSC Genome Browser. *Bioinformatics*. 2014;30(7):1003-5.
27. Haberle V, Forrest AR, Hayashizaki Y, Carninci P, Lenhard B. CAGEr: precise TSS data retrieval and high-resolution promoterome mining for integrative analyses. *Nucleic acids research*. 2015;43(8):e51-e.
28. MacFarland TW, Yates JM. Mann–whitney u test. *Introduction to nonparametric statistics for the biological sciences using R*: Springer; 2016. p. 103-32.
29. Benjamini Y, Hochberg Y. Controlling the false discovery rate: a practical and powerful approach to multiple testing. *Journal of the Royal statistical society: series B (Methodological)*. 1995;57(1):289-300.
30. Wulf MG, Maguire S, Humbert P, Dai N, Bei Y, Nichols NM, et al. Non-templated addition and template switching by Moloney murine leukemia virus (MMLV)-based reverse transcriptases co-occur and compete with each other. *Journal of Biological Chemistry*. 2019;294(48):18220-31.
31. Ohtake H, Ohtoko K, Ishimaru Y, Kato S. Determination of the capped site sequence of mRNA based on the detection of cap-dependent nucleotide addition using an anchor ligation method. *DNA research*. 2004;11(4):305-9.
32. Andrews S. A quality control tool for high throughput sequence data. 2010 [Available from: <https://www.bioinformatics.babraham.ac.uk/projects/fastqc/>].
33. Pennacchio LA, Bickmore W, Dean A, Nobrega MA, Bejerano G. Enhancers: five essential questions. *Nature Reviews Genetics*. 2013;14(4):288-95.

34. Balwierz PJ, Carninci P, Daub CO, Kawai J, Hayashizaki Y, Van Belle W, et al. Methods for analyzing deep sequencing expression data: constructing the human and mouse promoterome with deepCAGE data. *Genome biology*. 2009;10(7):R79.
35. Kaur G, Perteghella T, Carbonell-Sala S, Gonzalez-Martinez J, Hunt T, Mądry T, et al. GENCODE: massively expanding the lncRNA catalog through capture long-read RNA sequencing. *bioRxiv*. 2024.
36. Mudge JM, Carbonell-Sala S, Diekhans M, Martinez JG, Hunt T, Jungreis I, et al. GENCODE 2025: reference gene annotation for human and mouse. *Nucleic acids research*. 2025;53(D1):D966-D75.
37. Yip CW, Parr C, Takahashi H, Yasuzawa K, Valentine M, Nishiyori-Sueki H, et al. CFC-seq: identification of full-length capped RNAs unveil enhancer-derived transcription. *bioRxiv*. 2024:2024.10.31.620483.
38. Borsari B, Villegas-Mirón P, Pérez-Lluch S, Turpin I, Laayouni H, Segarra-Casas A, et al. Enhancers with tissue-specific activity are enriched in intronic regions. *Genome research*. 2021;31(8):1325-36.
39. Heintzman ND, Hon GC, Hawkins RD, Kheradpour P, Stark A, Harp LF, et al. Histone modifications at human enhancers reflect global cell-type-specific gene expression. *Nature*. 2009;459(7243):108-12.
40. Andersson R, Gebhard C, Miguel-Escalada I, Hoof I, Bornholdt J, Boyd M, et al. An atlas of active enhancers across human cell types and tissues. *Nature*. 2014;507(7493):455-61.
41. Haberman N, Digby H, Faraway R, Cheung R, Chakrabarti AM, Jobbins AM, et al. Widespread 3' UTR capped RNAs derive from G-rich regions in proximity to AGO2 binding sites. *BMC biology*. 2024;22(1):254.
42. Tripathi V, Ellis JD, Shen Z, Song DY, Pan Q, Watt AT, et al. The nuclear-retained noncoding RNA MALAT1 regulates alternative splicing by modulating SR splicing factor phosphorylation. *Molecular cell*. 2010;39(6):925-38.
43. Bergstrand S, O'Brien EM, Coucoravas C, Hrossova D, Peirasmaki D, Schmidli S, et al. Small Cajal body-associated RNA 2 (scaRNA2) regulates DNA repair pathway choice by inhibiting DNA-PK. *Nature communications*. 2022;13(1):1015.
44. West JA, Davis CP, Sunwoo H, Simon MD, Sadreyev RI, Wang PI, et al. The long noncoding RNAs NEAT1 and MALAT1 bind active chromatin sites. *Molecular cell*. 2014;55(5):791-802.
45. Zhang X, Hamblin MH, Yin K-J. The long noncoding RNA Malat1: Its physiological and pathophysiological functions. *RNA biology*. 2017;14(12):1705-14.